

The influence of accounting students' personality traits toward their entrepreneurship intention

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ABSTRACT

This paper intends to explore entrepreneurship intention among the youth by examining their personality traits. The respondents of this study were accounting students in their final year from seven public universities across Malaysia. A validated questionnaire was employed and distributed to representatives of each university, obtaining a total of 756 responses. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and utilized partial least square-structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) to analyze the hypotheses. The results revealed that personality traits influence entrepreneurship intention of accounting students' and conscientiousness being the most significant trait with a coefficient of 0.612. This paper suggests that personality traits namely conscientiousness, extraversion, openness to experience and agreeableness can boost entrepreneurship attitude, thus it should be optimized systematically into the education context to shape young personalities that are inclined towards entrepreneurship. Essentially, Ministry of Higher Institution, universities, colleges, and schools are advised to shape entrepreneurial personalities through the education curriculum and frequent practical sessions with inspiring entrepreneurs in the industry. Further, integrating the elements of personality traits into entrepreneurship education can serve as a guide for financial management of a business.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Malaysia aspires to become an entrepreneurial nation by the year 2030 and in achieving such ambitious goal, the National Entrepreneurship Policy (NEP) 2030 has been put in place by the Malaysian government which consists of long-term strategies, covering a wide range of aspects [1]. The policy aims to provide a holistic and conducive entrepreneurship environment to support entrepreneurs in running a business, instill entrepreneurship mindset among the nation, increase the number of competent, resilient, competitive entrepreneurs, enhance capabilities of micro, small and medium enterprises and ultimately make entrepreneurship as a preferred career choice. Essentially, entrepreneurship can resolve unemployment issues in the country, alongside boosting economic growth [2]. Thus, entrepreneurs within the local community needs to be encouraged to maintain long-term socio-economic sustainability. It is vital that entrepreneurship

is perceived as an attractive profession among the individuals, especially youth in Malaysia to encourage their participation in venture creation.

Along with this, entrepreneurship education is expected to motivate the youth to become entrepreneurs. In Malaysia, the Ministry of Higher Education (MoHE) has made it compulsory for all students enrolled in public universities to register for entrepreneurship courses as an initiative to instill entrepreneurship mindset within graduates [3]. Therefore, it is consequential that the entrepreneurship education is continuously refined to ensure it remains effective in encouraging the youth to choose entrepreneurial as their profession. In refining entrepreneurship education, great importance needs to be placed in developing the youths' entrepreneurship intention through their individual personalities, since entrepreneurial passion is shaped by an individuals' stable personality traits [4]. Personality traits of individuals can also be a contributing factor for igniting entrepreneurship intention [5]. Through this, individuals are more likely to find entrepreneurship as an attractive career to pursue passionately rather than opting to become an entrepreneur due to desperation.

Nevertheless, several issues related to individual-related skills need to be addressed to encourage entrepreneurial participation among the youth. The NEP 2030 affirms that the economic success of entrepreneurs relies heavily on their own efforts and skills, regardless of the external support provided from other parties [1]. Entrepreneurial behavior can be developed through entrepreneurial attitude which is influenced by the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education and understanding of individual personality traits [6]. Attitude has its associations with the personality traits of individuals, and it can bring changes to one's personality including their capabilities which makes them different from other individuals [7].

Despite this, there are still limited research sampling accounting undergraduates' personalities towards entrepreneurship intention in Malaysia. Accounting students' may be more inclined towards entrepreneurship since they are already equipped with financial and accounting knowledge that can be beneficial during their venture creation. In addition, identifying related personalities may assist scholars and policy makers to refine educational programs to build and enhance personalities to create intention towards entrepreneurship among youth.

Personality attributes are often associated with the development of entrepreneurial intentions since these traits are vital in determining individual behaviors [8]. Personality traits differ between one person to another, which makes every individual unique. These traits allow individuals to develop different interests based on their varying attributes. This also applies to their desired career choice, since every individual will be inclined to a certain career of their preference based on their traits. Although every individual has a unique set of personality traits, there may certain traits that allow an individual to develop the intention to become entrepreneurs. Essentially, entrepreneurs are believed to have certain identifiable characteristics and personality dimensions that can stimulate their intentions to dive into venture creation [9]. To affirm, it was found that the psychological profile of entrepreneurs and students who have high entrepreneurial intention are similar [10]. These results were characterized by specific personality traits which insinuates that certain personality traits can drive individuals to develop intentions to start their own business since the traits were found like those entrepreneurs who are already in the industry.

There are a wide range of personality traits to be studied in association with igniting entrepreneurship intention and the most common traits are need for achievement, risk-taking propensity as well as locus of control. These attributes which was referred to as "The Big Three" by Chell *et al.* [11] was used in the study of Farrukh *et al.* [12], where need for achievement, risk-taking propensity and locus of control was incorporated into the theory of planned behavior and associated with student entrepreneurial intention. As for personality traits, students with high need for achievement, risk taking tendency and locus of control are more likely to initiate business intentions only when they have the confidence and believe the decision is worthy. Many of these traits are related to the nature of entrepreneurship and play a role in entrepreneurial preparedness, intention, and success. For instance, the intention to become entrepreneurs can be realized when individuals have a higher level of entrepreneurial self-efficacy [5], and a high need for achievement [13]. It is apparent that specific personality traits that are related to entrepreneurship play a role in affecting entrepreneurial intent and success [14].

Further, the big five personality traits model have also been used in relation to study entrepreneurship intention [5], [6], [15]. The big five personality traits model is considered the most appropriate in explaining entrepreneurship intention [16], since it is applicable in assessing individual personality [10], [16], and how it can influence individuals' mindsets to dive into entrepreneurship. The model consists of five personality traits dimensions which are openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism [17].

Openness to experience relates to the willingness of an individual to try out new things, and their curiosity for new intellectual beliefs, ideas, and concepts [18], [19]. The conscientiousness dimension indicates that individuals are responsible, diligent, well-planned, and organized in whatever they do [18], [19]. It is also related to a high need for achievement and motivation to achieve goals, and these traits are

most likely what encourages individuals to become entrepreneurs [20], [21]. Extraversion is seen from the perspective of an individual's comfort level in relationships [6]. Individuals who are extraverted tend to be more sociable and can easily establish a network of connections with others since they are more outgoing and talkative. Agreeableness is the degree to which individuals are trusting, loving, and forgiving. The higher the level of agreeableness, the higher the level of trust and care. Lastly, neuroticism defines one's level of emotional stability. Individuals are more emotionally stable if they can handle their emotions well under stressful situations [15], [22]. As for neuroticism it has a negative impact on entrepreneurship, thus neuroticism is excluded in this study [22].

Based on the discussion, this paper aims to explore youth entrepreneurship intention by examine into their individual personality traits. The hypotheses for this study are: i) there is a positive effect of agreeableness on accounting undergraduate's entrepreneurship intention (H_1); ii) there is a positive effect of conscientiousness on accounting undergraduate's entrepreneurship intention (H_2); iii) there is a positive effect of extraversion on accounting undergraduate's entrepreneurship intention (H_3); and iv) there is a positive effect of openness to experience on accounting undergraduate's entrepreneurship intention (H_4).

2. METHOD

The quantitative approach is employed to collect information on accounting students' profile and the corresponding variables that influence entrepreneurship intention. A questionnaire instrument was utilized to explore the effect of personality traits toward entrepreneurship intention among accounting students. The respondent consisted of 756 accounting undergraduates from seven public universities that offered bachelor of accounting degree in Malaysia. The sample size will be determined according to the estimation calculation by Krejcie and Morgan stated that the sample size for a total population of 4,500 is 354 accounting undergraduates. Thus, 756 respondents are adequate for this study. Further, accounting program are designed based on a theoretical framework that embraces business understanding, skills and knowledge that are useful in business start-ups [23], which makes accounting undergraduates probable candidates of future entrepreneurs given the context of the educational programs offered in their courses.

The questionnaire is divided into three sections, starting with section A for demographic profile, section B consist of 18 items measuring four dimension of personality traits and section C contain six items measuring entrepreneurship intentions. The questionnaire is assembled through the adaptation of Big Five Model [24] and instrument developed by Liñán and Chen [25] to measure entrepreneurship intention from the basis of the theory of planned behavior. This study opted to use the 6-point Likert scale since it is preferred to direct the respondents towards one side of the spectrum [26] which ranges from 1 as "strongly disagree" to 6 as "strongly agree". Data analysis of this study is conducted using descriptive and inferential analysis. The main analysis utilized partial least square-structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) to analyze the hypotheses.

3. RESULTS

The data for this study was collected from accounting students enrolled in seven public universities in Malaysia over a period of four month. A total of 756 of respondents were involved in the study. The respondents are made up of 484 (64%) female students and 272 (35.9%) male students. With regards to the age, 48.5% of the respondents are between 19 to 22 years old, followed by respondents between the age of 23 to 25 which amount 395 (52.2%). The highest number of respondents are enrolled in Universiti Teknologi Mara (UiTM), with a total percentage of 16.1% (122) respondents, followed by Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia which percentage of 15.7% (119) respondents and Universiti Utara Malaysia with percentage of 15.6% (118) respondents, next is Universiti Sains Malaysia with 14.5% (110) respondents. Meanwhile Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris accounts for 14.0% (106) respondents. Both Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM) and Universiti Malaysia Terengganu (UMT) contributed to 12.8% (97) and 11.1% (84) respondents.

3.1. Reliability and validity

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted to verify the factor structure of a set of observed variables [26]. CFA was done by assessing the measurement model in two stage to measure reliability and validity and explains the relationship between indicators and its respective constructs. Evaluation of both the lower order construct (LOC) and higher-order construct (HOC) measurement models is done by evaluating the internal consistency, convergent validity as well as discriminant validity.

3.1.1. Stage 1: assessment of lower order construct measurement model

Using the repeated indicator's approach in the first stage, all indicators of the respective LOC are assigned as indicators of the HOC. Internal consistency was of the LOC were assessed by using the

Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability. The values of Cronbach's alpha for all LOCs were above the recommended value of 0.7 which was suggested by Hair *et al.* [27]. Convergent validity of the LOCs was assessed through both the factor loadings and average variance extracted (AVE). Essentially, factor loadings above 0.7 are retained for further analysis. Further, AVE values all exceed recommended amount of 0.5 [28]. Hence, convergent validity is met for LOCs. Table 1 presents the values for Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, factor loadings and AVE.

Table 1. Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, factor loading and AVE for LOCs

LOC	Indicators	Factor loadings (>0.6)	Cronbach's alpha (>0.7)	Composite reliability (rho c) (>0.7)	(AVE) (>0.5)
Agreeableness	A1 I am very sympathetic towards others.	0.844	0.892	0.921	0.699
	A2 I am considerate towards others.	0.861			
	A3 I am usually concerned about other people's problems.	0.867			
	A4 I am cooperative towards others.	0.822			
	A5 I always feel other's emotions.	0.785			
Conscientiousness	C1 I am highly motivated to achieve my goals.	0.827	0.822	0.882	0.653
	C2 I schedule my tasks according to priority.	0.773			
	C3 I always remember to put things back in their proper place.	0.771			
	C4 I am organized in dealing with things.	0.857			
Extraversion	E1 I find it easy to socialize with others.	0.908	0.922	0.941	0.763
	E2 I find it easy to initiate the conversation with others.	0.910			
	E3 I love to build networks with others.	0.838			
	E4 I think I am the life of any social gathering.	0.910			
	E5 I want to be highlighted/ the center of attention.	0.796			
Entrepreneurship intention	EI1 I firmly intend to establish my own business after I graduate	0.901	0.957	0.965	0.823
	EI2 I will work hard to start my own business.	0.881			
	EI3 My ambition is to become an entrepreneur.	0.893			
	EI4 I have seriously thought about starting my own business.	0.918			
	EI5 I am determined to create a business in the future.	0.937			
	EI6 I am ready to strive to be an entrepreneur.	0.912			
Openness to experience	O1 I have a good imagination	0.798	0.777	0.857	0.600
	O2 I have a creative imagination	0.799			
	O3 I am curious about new ideas.	0.770			
	O4 I am interested in trying out new experiences	0.729			

3.1.2. Stage 2: assessment of higher-order construct measurement model

The measurement model for the assessment of HOCs are drawn by using the LOC scores from the first stage. In other words, the LOC scores are used as indicators for the HOC's measurement model. The internal consistency of the HOC measurement model is assessed through Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability. All HOC exceed cut-off value suggested by Hair *et al.* [27]. For composite reliability, all HOCs exceed 0.7. Thus, it can be said that internal consistency is achieved for HOCs. Convergent validity of the HOCs was assessed by evaluating outer loading values and AVE. Following the criteria in stage 1, outer loadings above 0.6 are retained. All outer loading values for HOCs exceed 0.6; hence, thus no items were deleted. Further, all AVE values for HOCs exceed 0.5 as recommended by Hair *et al.* [28]. Therefore, it can be concluded that convergent validity is achieved. The values for Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, outer loadings, and AVE are demonstrated in Table 2.

Table 2. Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, outer loadings, and AVE for HOCs

HOC	Indicators	Factor loadings (>0.6)	Cronbach's alpha (>0.7)	Composite reliability (rho c) (>0.7)	(AVE) (>0.5)
Entrepreneurship spirit	ES1	0.901	0.957	0.965	0.823
	ES2	0.880			
	ES3	0.898			
	ES4	0.918			
	ES5	0.934			
	ES6	0.914			
Personality traits	O	0.782	0.793	0.861	0.609
	C	0.818			
	E	0.799			
	A	0.718			

3.2. Hypothesis testing

Statistical significance of the hypothesized relationships is evaluated using t-statistics and p-values. Table 3 represent the direct effect of the variables. As shown in Table 3, the direct effect of agreeableness on entrepreneurship intention is significant (path coeff.=0.529; $t=6.130$, $p<0.05$), therefore the first hypothesis is accepted. the finding can be interpreted as accounting students with a higher value of agreeableness having a higher intention to entrepreneurship. Next, the conscientiousness effect on entrepreneurship intention (path coeff.=0.612; $t=11.612$, $p<0.05$) is significantly proven. The second hypothesis was supported and concluded that conscientiousness had a direct influence on entrepreneurship intention. Further, extraversion (path coeff.=0.359; $t=7.986$, $p<0.05$) and openness to experience (path coeff.=0.437; $t=5.584$, $p<0.05$) are significant too. Therefore, this means that personality traits of agreeableness, conscientiousness, extraversion, and openness to experience influence entrepreneurship intention among accounting students.

Table 3. Hypotheses testing

	β	Standard deviation	T statistics	P values
A->ES	0.529	0.089	6.130	0.000
C->ES	0.612	0.046	11.612	0.000
E->ES	0.359	0.080	7.986	0.000
O->ES	0.437	0.079	5.584	0.000

4. DISCUSSION

This study has proven that personality traits of accounting undergraduates make a significant impact on their entrepreneurship intention. The outcome suggests that the four personality dimensions can be optimized as an approach to increase the spirit of entrepreneurship among accounting undergraduates since entrepreneurs are assumed to have certain identifiable characteristics that shape their interest towards entrepreneurship [29]. Among the four dimensions, conscientiousness became the most significant trait in impacting entrepreneurship intention since it produced the highest loading value. Conscientiousness is highly relevant in the context of entrepreneurship since it explains one's control over behavior, the drive to achieve goals, determination, dedication, hard work, being organized and responsible [30]. Previous research [31] argued that these traits not only build entrepreneurship interests, but they also shape necessary competencies that drive individuals to become successful entrepreneurs. Due to this, more emphasis should be given to enhance conscientious traits among the youth to shape entrepreneurial personalities. Result suggests that these traits can be integrated indirectly into entrepreneurship education by giving the youth further insight on the advantages and attractiveness of entrepreneurship to ensure they have a positive perception on the profession. Through this, it can be expected that the youth will be more enthusiastic in venture creation since they are driven by their own psychological traits.

Next, extraversion relates to individual traits in any given social relationship. These traits help individuals to communicate with others easily since they tend to be more assertive, warm, active, sociable, energetic, and emphatic as acknowledged by Şahin *et al.* [5]. The result is consistent with study by Costa and McCrae [20] which highlighted that entrepreneurs must connect with a wide range of constituents, developing an enhanced extraversion trait at an early stage during education is significant in operating a business. This is especially important during a time where resources are limited due to recent virus outbreak, in addition to Russia-Ukraine war and Palestine-Israel conflict where some resources have been cut short. Extraversion traits can be refined among students in higher education through coordination of practical entrepreneurship activities that require the students to be proactive and communicate effectively in a problem-solving situation [32]. In a way, this may push the students to become extroverted and at the same time create enthusiasm in diving into entrepreneurship.

Openness to experience is the tendency for individuals to be willing to try new things and experiences, while at the same time be adaptable in any situation. It also relates highly to being imaginative, creative, and adventurous which are important elements of entrepreneurship [32]. This result is in line with the research [33], which argued that entrepreneurship is closely tied to novelty, the necessity to explore and experience new things is important to bring something new and different to the industry. Therefore, these traits need to be nurtured through education, to ensure that the youth have the willingness to explore new possibilities [33]. The educational system should encourage the youth to participate in numerous conferences and seminars regarding the changes in the economy, or the current issues that need to be overcome [34]. These exposures could spark the youths' interests in exploring new ideas and at the same time indulge in new opportunities that they can benefit from in venture creation [35].

Finally, the finding illustrates that agreeableness trait has been identified to have a significant impact on individual interpersonal orientation. As discussed by Sadiq and Khan [36], these traits can be

beneficial in the conduct of an enterprise since agreeable traits explain tolerance, assertiveness, and benevolence. Further, expression of agreeableness leads to cooperation, social harmony and developing understanding of others' concerns [36], [37]. Juhari *et al.* [37] acknowledged that entrepreneurs, as leaders, should have a sense of agreeableness to a certain extent to ensure that their employees have a voice and at the same time be heard in making business decisions. Allowing the youth to participate in teamwork-based activities and assignments that are closely tied to entrepreneurship can enhance the extent to which they have control over their agreeableness traits [6], [38]. In addition, constructive discussions are also expected to give the youth the ability to have authority over their agreeable personalities.

5. CONCLUSION

These personality traits namely conscientiousness, extraversion, openness to experience and agreeableness should be optimized in enhancing entrepreneurship education in higher education. Since these traits have been defined to increase entrepreneurship intention among accounting undergraduates, it should be implemented systematically into the education context to shape young personalities that are inclined towards entrepreneurship. Further, the literature also suggests that the combination of personality traits and entrepreneurship education can significantly increase youth interest in entrepreneurship attitude. Therefore, higher institutions should design a more integrated curriculum and effective policy mechanism should be developed by policy maker to boost students' entrepreneurship intention.

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